

BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF MULTILAYERED BEAMS WITH SOFT AND RIGID INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

The paper revisits a fundamental problem of buckling behaviour of transversely isotropic multilayered beams with thin and soft interfaces. As a first step in providing a better understanding of wrinkle formation, the buckling behaviour of laminated beams under a compressive load is examined using available analytical and numerical (FE) approaches. In particular, we examine the ability of commercial finite element tools available to design engineers, e.g. ABAQUS composite editor, in simulating the bending and buckling behaviour of layered systems separated by relatively soft viscoelastic layers occurring in manufacturing of a range of composite products. It is demonstrated that by physically modelling the thin interfaces between plies using solid elements, the significant reduction of critical buckling load for laminates with soft interfaces could be captured.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their superior specific properties, laminated composites such as carbon fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRPs) and laminated veneer lumber (LVL) are widely being used in the aerospace, automotive, and construction industry. However, there are still challenges involved that prevent the realisation of the full potential of these materials in engineering applications. Wrinkle formation during manufacturing is among these challenges. Wrinkles often lead to reduction of mechanical part performance.

Although there are numerous studies on the formation of wrinkles in textile composites, the three-dimensional (3D) formation of wrinkles is not fully understood for other composites, especially those being used in the construction sector. As mentioned in Dodwell et al.'s studies [1, 2], in addition to shear-induced high compressive stresses due to geometrical features, buckling instabilities are more likely to occur when carbon fibre layers have excess length and restrained from slipping over one another due to friction or fixed ends.

A variety of numerical models have been developed for predicting consolidation-induced wrinkles. Dodwell proposed simplified one-dimensional [2] and two-dimensional [1] models for capturing wrinkling during consolidation of unidirectional (UD) laminates over an external radius. Although these two models could be used as design tools for parts with a corner radius, their abilities to consider other 3D complex geometries with including directional nature of different plies have not been investigated. Linear buckling analysis of anisotropic laminated plates under combined biaxial and shear loading during service life was conducted by Nali [3] using two-dimensional numerical models;

however, the study focused on only cured laminates. For a better understanding of the manufacturing trials, a predictive FE model for wrinkle formation was also implemented by Belnoue [4]. Linear reduced integration solid elements (C3D8R) in ABAQUS were used and a dynamic implicit analysis was performed. Nevertheless, much attention was given to L- and C-sections to determine the influences of different boundary conditions. To the authors' knowledge, the wrinkle formation in flat laminates (e.g. those used in the construction industry) has not been investigated in detail.

The present study revisits a more fundamental problem of buckling behaviour of isotropic and transversely isotropic multilayered beams with thin and soft interfaces. As a first step in providing a better understanding of wrinkle formation, the buckling behaviour of laminated beams under compressive loads are examined using various analytical and numerical approaches. In particular, we examine the capability of commercial numerical tools available to design engineers, e.g. composite editor in ABAQUS, in simulating the buckling behaviour of layered systems separated by relatively soft viscoelastic layers occurring in manufacturing of a range of laminated composite products.

2 METHODOLOGY

Three-dimensional multilayered beams are modelled using two approaches; (i) layup composite editor for 3D solid composite elements and (ii) physical modelling of individual layers (with 3D solid elements) and interfaces within ABAQUS environment. Each model is composed of $N = 48$ identical stiff layers which are separated by $N - 1$ soft interfaces similar to reference [1]. The thicknesses of a single layer (ply), t_p , and an interface, t_i , are 0.2 mm and 0.01 mm, respectively, thereby the total thickness of the multilayered beam is $T = Nt_p + (N - 1)t_i$. The generated multilayered beam is 50 mm of length and 1 mm width (h). For verification purposes, both materials are initially assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic. While E_p and ν_p , the material properties of the layers, are kept unchanged and equal to 100 GPa and 0.2, respectively, E_i takes a range of values which define the material properties of the interfaces. Identical Poisson's ratio were used for plies and interfaces (i.e. $\nu_p = \nu_i$).

Using the first approach, the composite characteristic is defined by a composite layup tool in the property module of ABAQUS CAE as demonstrated in Fig. 1. In the second approach, the beam geometry is partitioned into physical layers (thickness of 0.2 mm) separated by distinct interfaces (thickness of 0.01 mm) before they are meshed and the material properties are assigned.

Figure 1: Composite layup

To verify the model, the deformation behaviour of multilayered cantilever beams with a range of interface stiffness under a vertical displacement is examined (Case I). Results are compared with a simple beam bending equation to highlight the need for more sophisticated elements or approaches in this area. Then, the critical buckling loads and the first mode shapes of flat laminates with soft interfaces are compared with those with stiff ones (Case II). The critical buckling loads are presented

and compared with Euler buckling estimates. In both cases, the effect of ply anisotropy on the buckling behaviour of laminates with soft and stiff interfaces is investigated.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Case I - Multilayered cantilever beam under bending

A 1mm x 10.07mm x 50 mm multilayered cantilever beam is modelled using a 20-node quadratic brick element with reduced integration element (C3D20R) and mesh size of 0.2 mm. The elastic behaviour of this beam is first examined using the PML approach. While one end of the beam is fixed, a vertical displacement equal to $\Delta = 0.2$ mm is applied to the other end. Both the layers and interfaces are assumed to be isotropic in Case I. The force, P , at the free edge corresponding to the vertical displacement of 0.2 mm is obtained from finite element analysis and compared with the one calculated from the principles of mechanics of materials, i.e. equation below:

$$\Delta = \frac{PL^3}{3EI} \quad (1)$$

Where EI is the flexural rigidity of the cantilever beam section. Three cases corresponding to three different values of E_i (interface modulus) are considered; starting at the same stiffness of ply modulus E_i (100 GPa) and reducing by a factor of 10 for the other two subsequent cases.

E_i (GPa)	P (kN)		
	PML _{FE} (Present)	FE (Dodwell)	Analytical
100	4.485E-02	4.500E-02	4.617E-02
1	3.769E-02	3.800E-02	4.412E-02
0.01	3.085E-03	3.000E-03	4.410E-02

Table 1: Comparisons between current FE predictions, Dodwell’s FE results [1], and the analytical model (Eq. 1) for a multilayered cantilever beam (Case I).

Table 1 highlights a good agreement between results from the present finite element analysis with Dodwell’s FE model for all three cases and analytical calculation when E_i equals E_p , 100 GPa. Hence, the PML is verified against analytical solutions when $E_i = E_p = 100$ GPa. It should be noted that only the bending deformation has been considered in Eq. (1). When $E_i = E_p = 100$ GPa, the contribution of shear deformation is negligible and the multilayered cantilever deforms as a solid isotropic beam based on the assumptions of Eq. (1). In contrast, for the subsequent cases with soft interfaces, the layers are more likely to bend more independently due to excessive shear deformations at the interfaces, reducing the apparent flexural rigidity of the entire beam.

To better understand the role of ply anisotropy on the overall beam rigidity, three more cases with transversely isotropic layers are considered. The elastic constants of such layers are listed in Table 2.

Properties	Value
E_{1p} , GPa	100
E_{2p} , GPa	8
G_{12p} , GPa	3.98
G_{23p} , GPa	2.86
ν_{12p}	0.26
ν_{23p}	0.4

Table 2: Input properties of the transversely isotropic plies.

Figure 2: The role of interface stiffness and ply anisotropy on the multilayered cantilever beam rigidity.

Figure 2 highlights the role of interface stiffness for isotropic and transversely isotropic laminates. As the interface becomes soft ($E_i = 0.01$ GPa), the beam flexural rigidity is significantly reduced irrespective of the ply orthotropic nature. In other words, the soft interface dominates the bending response (e.g. uncured prepregs and laminates during cure). However, the beam bending behaviour is dominated by the engineering constants of the plies when the interface is stiff ($1 \text{ GPa} < E_i < 100 \text{ GPa}$). In other words, we could assume that plies are almost perfectly bonded when the interface is relatively stiff (cured laminates).

3.2 Case 2 - Flat laminate under compressive load

The buckling behaviour of a flat laminate (10.07x1x50mm) is considered here using two different approaches; ABAQUS built-in composite editor (CE) and physically modelling layers (PML). Similar cases are also considered with transversely isotropic material properties to understand the role of ply anisotropy on the laminate buckling response.

3.2.1 Two pinned ends

First, the laminate is pin supported and a uniform axial pressure on the free end face is applied. Such a simple buckling scenario is considered because there is an existing analytical solution for verification purposes. The FE results using eigenvalue analyses for both approaches mentioned above along with Euler predictions are summarized in Fig. 3. Five interface properties, E_i , ranging from 100 kPa to 100 GPa, equal to constant E_p , are also introduced to investigate the influence of interface stiffness on the overall buckling behaviors.

As seen in Fig. 3, results from CE analyses correlate well with Euler solutions for all cases and a slight increase is presented as the interface becomes more rigid. With PML models, critical buckling loads reduce significantly in comparison with those obtained from the two remaining methods when the interfaces are much softer than the plies ($E_i \leq 1$ MPa). Specially, Euler prediction as well as CE result as $E_i = 100$ kPa is more than 10 times of PML solution (31 MPa compared to 3 MPa).

The shapes of buckled beams with stiff interfaces ($E_i = 100$ GPa) are plotted in Fig. 4 and 5 for CE and PML models respectively. Both mode shapes are identical and buckle in y-plane. However, only PML analysis can capture buckling deformation when the interfaces are very soft (Fig. 6). The

laminates bends in x-plane, meaning that the layers buckle as N independent beams. The critical buckling stress is therefore dropped significantly, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure. 3: Comparisons of FE results with Euler predictions for isotropic plies ($E_p = 100$ GPa) bonded with a range of interfaces.

Figure. 4: (a) Buckling mode shape for flat laminates with stiff interfaces ($E_i = 100$ GPa) using PML approach. The beam cross section is depicted on the right side.

Figure. 5: Buckling mode shape for flat laminates with stiff interfaces ($E_i = 100$ GPa) using ABAQUS CE. The laminate layup is depicted on the right side for clarity.

Figure. 6: Buckling mode shape for flat laminates with soft interfaces ($E_i = 100$ kPa) using PML approach.

Similar to Case I, the effect of ply anisotropy on the buckling behaviour of laminates is investigated by using PML models and results are presented in Fig. 7. Two different transversely isotropic properties listed in Table 2 and 3 are used for comparison. When the transverse Young's modulus and shear moduli are still high (Table 2) their effects on the buckling response are negligible (Fig. 7). Results also demonstrate the less significant effect of ply anisotropy compared to the interface stiffness. The interface stiffness (or the presence of resin rich areas between the plies) dominates the buckling response of flat laminates similar to their bending response presented in Case I. During composite processing, the resin modulus may decrease quite significantly. This could lead to formation of wrinkles (buckled plies) under much lower compressive loads which needs to be captured accurately.

Properties	Value
E_{1p} , GPa	100
E_{2p} , GPa	0.8
G_{12p} , GPa	0.398
G_{23p} , GPa	0.286
ν_{12p}	0.26
ν_{23p}	0.4

Table 3: Input properties of the transversely isotropic plies.

Figure. 7: The influence of ply elastic constants on the buckling response of flat laminates using PML.

3.2.2 Four fixed edges

To look at the role of manufacturing constraints, an additional boundary condition is applied for the two remaining edges of the laminate beam. It is to prevent plies from moving in the plane perpendicular to the compressive load direction, so that plies can buckle internally. Table 4 lists preliminary finite element results for beams with a range of interface properties. The four cases correspond to four values of starting with the same stiffness of ply modulus $E_p = 100$ GPa and reducing by a factor of 10 for subsequent cases.

	Laminate 1	Laminate 2	Laminate 3	Laminate 4
E_i (GPa)	0.1	1	10	100
$(P_{cr})_{CE}$ (N)	46420	46441	46650	48739
$(P_{cr})_{PML}$ (N)	6975.8	19152	39494	48698

Table 4: Comparisons of FE results between composite element models and models layered physically – $E_p = 100$ GPa for all cases

For the beams modelled using ABAQUS composite editor (CE), results show that as the interface becomes more rigid, the critical buckling load increases only slightly (see Table 4). In contrast, the critical buckling load reduces more than 6 times as the elastic modulus of the interfaces are reduced by

a factor 1000 (compare Laminate 1 and Laminate 4) for PML analyses. When the interface and ply modulus are identical (100 GPa), the minimum critical loads obtained using both approaches (CE and PML) are almost the same. As shown in Fig. 8, the composite laminate is buckled into seven half waves in the longitudinal direction for the stiff interface ($E_i = 100$ GPa). Similar mode shape is observed using PML approach for stiff interface as depicted in Fig. 9 (red line). However, the predicted critical buckling load (Table 4) and first mode shape of laminates with PML become quite different from those modelled using ABAQUS CE as the interfaces become soft. It is more likely that the soft interfaces dominate the overall buckling of the multilayered beams which cannot be captured with CE models. When the stiffness of the interfaces decreases, the internal buckling wavelength rises as seen in Fig. 9.

Figure. 8: Magnitude displacement (in mm) at critical buckling load – Composite element model - $E_2 = 100$ GPa

Figure. 9: Internal buckling wavelength along the beam length – Physically modelling layers

4 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The buckling analysis of multilayered composite beams using two different approaches was conducted. The performance of ABAQUS built-in composite editor were compared with physically modelling the individual plies and interfaces using solid elements. Results show that ABAQUS built-in composite element (CE) is only capable of estimating the composite critical buckling load when the mismatch between layers (plies) and the interface elastic modulus is relatively low. When the interfaces are soft (e.g. at the early stage of cure), a significant difference was demonstrated between finite element results obtained from the composite editor and the physically layered model as well as Euler's estimates. Therefore, alternative approaches or elements are required for simulating the deformation of laminates during composite processing accurately. It was demonstrated that by physically modelling the thin interfaces between plies, the significant reduction of critical buckling loads could be captured for laminates bonded with soft interfaces.

The proposed approach is an initial step towards implementing an orthotropic viscoelastic model for multi-scale process modelling of laminated composites with complex microstructures. Further work on incorporating the thermo-viscoelastic effect of plies and model validation using existing experimental data at different loading rates is currently underway.

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